

ACHIEVERS JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH*Open Access Publications of Achievers University, Owo*Available Online at www.achieversjournalofscience.org**Perception of Working Class Women on Utilization of Wood Cutting for Creative Home Furnishings for Economic Development****S.O. Abdulkadir¹, T.T. Adebisi², I.B. Adeniran³ and O.P. Abiola⁴**^{1,2,4}Department of Home-Economics and Food science, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Ilorin, Ilorin.³Department of Biological Sciences, College of Natural and Applied Sciences, Achievers University, Owo, Ondo State.Corresponding author: bello.os@unilorin.edu.ng

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Abstract

The paper investigated Perception of working class women on utilization of wood cutting for creative home furnishings for economic development. Six research questions were raised and Four hypotheses were formulated and tested. The population for this study comprised working class women in Okuku, Osun state. 200 working class women were used as sample. Questionnaire and score card were used for data collection. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics. Results of the study revealed that majority of the respondents have high level of awareness on utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing for homes, also durability, budget, comfort, aesthetic and styles, among others have influence on utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing. Creative furnishings are perceived as having the potential to add value, economics benefits, durable and aesthetic appeal to living spaces. Hypothetically, there is significant relationship between the potential economic benefits, factors that influence utilization of wood cutting for creative home furnishing and perception of working-class women towards creative home furnishing made from wood cutting ($p=0.000$), also there is no statistically significant correlation between challenges faced and the perception of working-class women towards creative home furnishing made from wood cutting ($P>0.089$). The study concluded that there was acceptability of utilization of wood cuttings for creative furnishing for economic developments and promotion of creativity. It was recommended that the use of creative furnishing from wood cuttings by the entrepreneurs will help to create more employment opportunity among the youth and elderly.

Keywords: Wood cutting, Home furnishing, Perception, Utilization, Economic development**1.0 Introduction**

In accordance with individual needs, individuals furnish and decorate their living spaces, leading them to purchase and utilize specific types of furnishings (Guzel, 2020). Furnishings are components or objects, such as chairs, curtains, tables, beddings and desks, which are used to establish inhabitable spaces in buildings and rooms (Yoon, 2018) and beautify the interior and

provide a pleasant atmosphere in the house. Such furnishing is purposefully designed and manufactured to serve distinct functions, including but not limited to seating, relaxation, studying, gaming, storage, display, and spatial division. Ertaş and Şatir (2021) defined furnishing as items that are utilized to adorn and furnish seating spaces for diverse purposes. As this definition implies, furnishings is a commodity that influences the effectiveness of a

space based on its functionality and aesthetic value, rendering it either appealing or unattractive.

Furnishing has been a critical component of human living environments throughout history and continues to play an essential role in creating comfortable conditions for survival (Yoon, 2018). The development of national and international furniture design systems and production processes reflects the complexity and controversy of modern requirements for furniture (Zheng and Zhu, 2021).

Currently, the furniture industry is placing a significant emphasis on environmental considerations and technological advancements in order to distinguish their products from those of competitors, and to tap into the emerging market for eco-friendly goods. Accordingly, the incorporation of environmentally sustainable design principles is viewed as a central aspect of this industry (Zen *et al.*, 2020). Despite this trend, furnishings made from wood remains a popular choice among customers due to its inherent natural and authentic qualities, which contribute to a pleasing and tranquil environment (Vuong, 2022). Moreover, the renewable and eco-friendly nature of wood, as well as its perceived health and safety benefits, are highly valued by consumers. As such, wood is favoured by many customers due to its traditional, natural, and ecological attributes.

The significance of wood furnishing in human living environments can be traced back to ancient times (Zheng and Zhu, 2021). It plays a vital role in the planning of buildings and enables spaces to function effectively. It is a product that merges art and technique and plays a vital role in enhancing the comfort, aesthetics, and liveliness of homes and workplaces (Wang, 2022). For instance, the living room, office spaces, concert halls, and schools all serve various purposes, and the design of furniture should be adapted to meet these diverse requirements. As such, furniture design is an essential aspect of creating functional spaces that serve multiple needs (Ertaş and Şatir, 2021).

Wood as a raw material is used for construction and production of several types of furniture such

as bed frames, chairs, tables, foot stools, and wall hangers among others. In Nigeria, the wood industry encompasses various sectors such as timber logging, sawmilling, the production of wood-based panel products, furniture manufacturing, paper making, and the manufacturing of wooden items. However, the demand for timber and its derived products has resulted in a significant amount of wood waste, such as sawdust, tree cut-offs, sliced wood, and tree bark. Unfortunately, these residues are often left unutilized or improperly disposed of, leading to environmental degradation.

Despite the importance of furniture design in enhancing the quality of life and creating functional living spaces, there is no understanding of the value and importance of sliced wood for both creative households and official furniture. Small woods that are cut or sliced during the wood-cutting process are disposed of or left underutilized, when utilized; the sliced wood can be transferred to wealth and can be used to generate income for the unemployed.

It is observed that the concept of using sliced wood in the production of affordable furnishings hasn't been met. It is important to determine how sliced wood waste can be transformed into the primary material for creative furniture design and to measure the perception of working-class women towards such designs. Therefore, this study assessed the perception of working-class women towards utilization of wood cutting for creative home furnishing for economic development.

2.0 Methodology

- a. **Research Design:** The study used research and development (R&D) design and survey research because it involves the production of creativity.
- b. **Population of the study:** The population for this study comprised working class women in Okuku, Osun state
- c. **Sampling technique:** The sampling of the respondents was done using purposive random sampling technique. It is purposive because it is targeted at a specific set of

people (working-class women) in Okuku. This study uses 10% of the population (2,187) which is estimated at 200 working class women.

- d. **Instrument for Data Collection:** the instruments used were questionnaire and score card (SC)
- e. **Validity of research instruments:** instruments were validated by research supervisor and two other lecturers in the Department of Home Economics and Food Science.
- f. **Reliability of research instrument:** pilot study was conducted using a sample size of 20 working class women in Okuku local government. The 20 subjects were not be part of the population involved in the study. The

data obtained from the pilot study was subjected to statistical analysis to determine the reliability of the instrument and the internal consistency of the items using Cronbach's alpha test of reliability. A coefficient of 0.70 was the benchmark of acceptance of reliability.

- g. **Materials:** Neems wood (*Azadirachta indica*), Mirror, Sticker, Exotic gum, Sand paper, Ply wood, Polish, Led light, Tape. The mirror was purchased at Ita-Amodu, Old Yidi Road, Ilorin, Kwara State. The wood cut was obtained from sawmill in Okuku. Exotic gum, frame, carton, polish, and sharp sandpaper were purchased at Orisunbare market, Osogbo, Osun state

Plate 1: Raw materials

Figure 1: Production of living room mirror and wall hanger

PLATE 2: Creative Bedroom mirror, Creative Dining room mirror, Creative Sitting room wall Design

3.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1: Level of awareness of working-class women on utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes

Table 1 presents the frequency, percentage, mean score, standard deviation and remarks on respondents' level of awareness on utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes. It reveals that majority of the respondents have high level of awareness on utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes this is because they have a mean score that are above the mid mean score of 1.50 except statement 1 and 7 which have mean scores below 1.50, which implies that respondents have low level of awareness on utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes. This is supported by the study of Inglis (2010) which revealed that consumer want to know about their furnishings where it is made, what it is made of, and how it is made. Consumer pay attention to wellness in their homes, sustainability has taken urgency in consumer purchases. Increasing consumer awareness could potentially influence more positive perceptions of these products among the target respondents.

3.2: Factors that influence the utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes by working-class women

Table 2 presents the frequency, percentage, mean score, standard deviation and remarks on factors that influence the utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes by working-class women. This table shows that respondents agreed to all identified factors that influence the utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes by working-class women; this is because they have mean score that are above the mid mean value of 1.50. This implies that respondents agreed that the listed factors that influence the utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes by working-class women Since all the items were agreed on thus, all respondents agreed that function, durability, budget, comfort,

aesthetic and styles, sustainable environment and lifestyles have influence on the utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes by working-class women. This agreed with the study of Al Horr et al. (2016) revealed that creating indoor environment that benefit the physical and mental health have effect

on comfort, productivity, and work performance positively. Also supported by the study of Tsunetsugu et al., (2007) which posited that natural environment have indicated to facilitate relaxation, reduce stress, and improve human mood and state as well as creativity.

Table 1: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of Respondents on level of awareness of working-class women on utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes

SNO	Questions	High F (%)	Low F (%)	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	Do you think your primary source of information should be only from the internet when shopping for new furniture?	17(11.3)	133(88.7)	1.11	0.32	Low
2.	Have you heard of creative furniture design?	114(76.0)	36(24.0)	1.76	0.43	High
3.	Have you ever purchased creative furniture design?	111(74.0)	39(26.0)	1.74	0.44	High
4.	Are you interested in creative furniture design?	114(76.0)	36(24.0)	1.76	0.43	High
5.	Is comfort a factor to consider when selecting creative furniture?	118(78.7)	32(21.3)	1.79	0.41	High
6.	Do Aesthetics/ design motivate you in choosing creative furniture?	135(90.0)	15(10.0)	1.90	0.30	High
7.	New furniture should only be purchased when the old one is broken?	56(37.3)	94(62.7)	1.37	0.49	Low
8.	Do you think reviews and recommendations matter while shopping for a new furniture?	117(78.0)	33(22.0)	1.78	0.42	High
9.	Should furniture be purchased based on size and proportion?	120(80.0)	30(20.0)	1.80	0.40	High
10.	Should brand reputation be considered while making a furniture Purchase?	111(74.0)	39(26.0)	1.74	0.44	High

Field Survey, 2023

3.3: Potential economic benefits of utilizing wood cuttings for creative furnishing designs for homes

Table 3 presents the frequency, percentage; mean score, standard deviation and remarks on economic benefits of utilizing wood cuttings for creative furnishing designs for homes. This table shows that creative furnishing from wood cutting has economic benefits; this is because the respondents agreed to all statements because they have mean score that are above the mid mean value of 1.50, this implies that creative

furnishing from wood cutting will new economic opportunities for local communities, job creation, local sales of wood products, reduce environmental waste and increase value for local timber. This agreed with the study of Maji et al., (2019) which revealed that wood is versatile and essential natural resources which is use for construction and has significant energy generation and other utilities. It is use for the production of several furniture e.g Table, foot stools, wall hangers among others.

Table 2: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of Respondents factors that influence the utilization of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes by working-class women

SNO	Statements	Agree F (%)	Disagree F (%)	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	While choosing a furniture, do you consider the functions	146(97.3)	4(2.7)	1.96	0.23	Agreed
2	Furniture should be purchased based on durability?	142(94.7)	8(5.3)	1.95	0.23	Agreed
3	Should budget determine furniture purchase?	141(94.0)	9(6.0)	1.94	0.24	Agreed
4	Styles and aesthetic should be considered	132(88.0)	18(12.0)	1.82	0.46	Agreed
5	Should maintenance and care of furniture matters while making a purchase?	127(84.7)	23(15.3)	1.81	0.44	Agreed
6	Should sustainable Environment determine a furniture purchase?	124(82.7)	26(17.3)	1.77	0.63	Agreed
7	Is comfortable part of determine factors for furniture purchase	141(94.0)	9(6.0)	1.91	0.35	Agreed
8	Should versatility of furniture be considered	135(90.0)	15(10.0)	1.86	0.40	Agreed
9	Are personal factors like; habits and lifestyle important while Planning furniture purchase?	134(89.3)	16(10.7)	1.65	0.70	Agreed

Field Survey, 2023

Table 3: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of Respondents on Potential economic benefits of utilizing wood cuttings for creative furnishing designs for homes

S/N	Statements	Beneficial F (%)	Not Beneficial F (%)	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Do you think using wood cuttings for creative home furnishings can create new economic opportunities for local communities?	144(96.0)	6(4.0)	1.91	0.40	Agreed
2	Can creative home furnishing create new jobs for local residents?	149(99.3)	1(0.7)	1.92	0.30	Agreed
3	Can using wood cuttings for creative home furnishings increase local sales of wood products?	145(96.7)	5(3.3)	1.97	0.18	Agreed
4	Do you think using wood cuttings for creative home furnishings will Reduce local waste?	144(96.0)	6(4.0)	1.83	0.47	Agreed
5	Do you think using wood cuttings for creative home furnishings could increase the value of local timber?	148(98.7)	2(1.3)	1.91	0.33	Agreed
6	Can lack of knowledge about using wood cuttings for creative home furnishings be a barrier to doing so?"	142(94.6)	8(5.3)	1.80	0.52	Agreed
7	Do you think creative home furnishings require little knowledge?	115(76.6)	35(23.3)	1.50	0.84	Agreed
8	Can better tools and techniques reduce the time required in creative furnishings?	126(84.0)	24(16.0)	1.57	0.75	Agreed

Field Survey, 2023

3.4: Challenges faced using produced creative home furnishing from wood cuttings

Table 4 presents the frequency, percentage, mean score, standard deviation and remarks challenges faced using produced creative home furnishing from wood cuttings. This table shows there are no challenges on utilization of wood cutting for creative home furnishings; this is because the respondents disagreed to all statements because they have mean score that are below the mid

mean value of 1.50, this implies utilization of wood cutting for creative home furnishing does not posed any challenges on the users. This disagreed with the study of Zhu et al. (2017) which revealed that interior design element is challenging because it depends on the designer's experience. Also the study of Weisset et al. (2020) also revealed that distinction between interior styles remain somewhat unclear.

Table 4: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of Respondents challenges faced using produced creative home furnishing from wood cuttings

S/N	Statements	Challenge F (%)	Not a Challenge F (%)	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Finding creative home furnishings products that match personal style is difficult	75(50.0)	75(50.0)	0.65	0.73	Disagreed
2	Is it difficult to find creative home furnishings products that fit within budgets?	44(29.3)	106(70.7)	0.33	0.54	Disagreed
3	Is it difficult to find products creative home furnishings that are durable and long-lasting?	18(12.0)	132(88.0)	0.15	0.45	Disagreed
4	Is it difficult to find creative home furnishings products that are easy to care for and maintain?	16(10.6)	134(89.3)	0.12	0.37	Disagreed
5	Do you think creative home furnishings products are not environmentally friendly?	23(15.3)	127(84.7)	0.20	0.51	Disagreed
6	Creative home furnishings products cannot be comfortable and functional	14(9.3)	136(90.7)	0.11	0.38	Disagreed
7	Creative home furnishings products are not available in the desired size	19(12.7)	131(87.3)	0.17	0.47	Disagreed
8	Creative home furnishings products are not suitable for aesthetic	27(18.0)	123(82.0)	0.26	0.60	Disagreed

Field Survey, 2023

3.5: Acceptability of produced creative home furnishings from wood cuttings

Table 5 shows the acceptability of participants on sampled bed room mirror coded CF1. The sampled bed room mirror mean scores based on appearance are 7.79, the finishing is 7.35, the style is 7.65, and the design is 7.19 while overall acceptability is 7.81. The mean scores of the data are greater than 4.00. This means that the

participants have acceptance of a bed room mirror from wood cutting for creative furnishing.

Table 6 shows the acceptability of participants on sampled dining room mirror coded CF2. The sampled bed room mirror mean scores based on appearance are 7.10, the finishing is 7.15, the style is 7.31, and the design is 7.15 while overall acceptability is 7.57. The mean scores of the data are greater than 4.00. This means that the

participants have acceptance of a dining room

mirror from wood cutting for creative furnishing.

Table 5: Sampled coded Bedroom mirror for Creative Furnishing

Samples	LE	LM	LS	UD	DS	DM	DE	Mean
CF1	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
Appearance	101(67.3)	24(16.0)	11(7.3)	2(1.3)	5(3.3)	2(1.3)	5(3.3)	7.79
Finishing	94(62.7)	24(16.0)	8(5.3)	6(4.0)	5(3.3)	3(2.0)	10(6.7)	7.35
Style	98(65.4)	23(15.3)	12(8.0)	4(2.7)	7(4.7)	1(0.7)	5(3.3)	7.65
Design	86(57.3)	21(14.0)	19(12.7)	4(2.7)	6(4.0)	3(2.0)	11(7.4)	7.19
Overall	111(74.0)	15(10.0)	10(6.7)	1(0.7)	6(4.0)	1(0.7)	6(4.0)	7.81
Acceptability								

Field Survey, 2023; LE/7=Like Extremely, LM/6=Like Moderately, LS/5=Like Slightly, UD/4=Undecided, DS/3=Dislike Slightly, DM/2=Dislike Moderately, DE/1=Dislike Extremely

Table 6: Sampled coded Dining Room mirror for Creative Furnishing

Samples	LE	LM	LS	UD	DS	DM	DE	Mean
CF2	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
Appearance	82(54.6)	33(22.0)	8(5.3)	3(2.0)	8(5.3)	-	16(10.7)	7.10
Finishing	96(64.0)	14(9.3)	6(4.0)	7(4.7)	8(5.3)	3(2.0)	16(10.7)	7.15
Style	92(61.3)	27(18.0)	8(5.3)	3(2.0)	4(2.7)	2(1.3)	14(9.3)	7.31
Design	89(59.4)	19(12.7)	13(8.7)	9(6.0)	3(2.0)	4(2.7)	13(8.7)	7.15
Overall	100(66.7)	22(14.7)	13(8.7)	1(0.7)	4(2.7)	1(0.7)	9(6.0)	7.57
Acceptability								

Field Survey, 2023; LE/7=Like Extremely, LM/6=Like Moderately, LS/5=Like Slightly, UD/4=Undecided, DS/3=Dislike Slightly, DM/2=Dislike Moderately, DE/1=Dislike Extremely

Table 7: Sampled coded Wall Design for Creative Furnishing

Samples	LE	LM	LS	UD	DS	DM	DE	Mean
CF3	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
Appearance	100(66.7)	23(15.3)	11(7.3)	4(2.7)	2(1.3)	5(3.3)	5(3.3)	7.69
Finishing	107(71.3)	23(15.3)	6(4.0)	4(2.7)	2(1.3)	2(1.3)	6(4.0)	7.80
Style	110(73.4)	13(8.7)	9(6.0)	3(2.0)	4(2.7)	2(1.3)	9(6.0)	7.75
Design	103(68.6)	30(20.0)	3(2.0)	2(1.3)	3(2.0)	2(1.3)	7(4.7)	7.77
Overall	107(71.3)	16(10.7)	7(4.7)	4(2.7)	5(3.3)	-	11(7.3)	7.64
Acceptability								

Field Survey, 2023; LE/7=Like Extremely, LM/6=Like Moderately, LS/5=Like Slightly, UD/4=Undecided, DS/3=Dislike Slightly, DM/2=Dislike Moderately, DE/1=Dislike Extremely

Table 7 shows the acceptability of participants on sampled wall design coded CF3. The sampled wall design mean scores based on appearance are 7.69, the finishing is 7.80, the style is 7.75, and the design is 7.77 while overall acceptability is 7.64. The mean scores of the data are greater than 4.00. This means that the participants have acceptance of a wall design from wood cutting for creative furnishing.

This implies that CF1 generally received higher ratings across visual attributes and overall

acceptability, suggesting it was the most favoured among the produced creative home furnishings.

3.6: Perception of working-class women on utilizations of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes

Table 8 presents the frequency, percentage, mean score, standard deviation and remarks on perception of working-class women on utilizations of wood cuttings for creative home

furnishing design for homes. This table shows respondents agreed to all the statements except statement 1; this is because they have mean score that are above the mid mean value of 2.50, this implies that the responses from working-class women indicate a generally positive perception of creative home furnishing design using wood cuttings. They perceive creative furniture as having the potential to add value, revenue, and

aesthetic appeal to living spaces, while also being durable and capable of personalization.

The table also shows that respondents disagreed to statement 1; this is because it has mean score that is below the mid mean value of 2.50, this implies that respondents did not perceive creative room furnishing from wood cutting for wealthy people only.

Table 8: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the perception of working-class women on utilizations of wood cuttings for creative home furnishing design for homes

SNO	Statements	Agree F (%)	Disagree F (%)	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Do you agree that creative furniture are for the wealthy?	7(4.7)	143(95.3)	1.32	0.58	Disagreed
2	Do you agree that creative furniture is not suited for families with younger children?	76(50.6)	74(49.3)	2.61	1.34	Agreed
3	Can creative furniture add to revenue generations	144(96.0)	6(4.0)	3.69	0.64	Agreed
4	Creative furniture adds to revenue generations?	142(94.7)	8(5.4)	3.71	0.65	Agreed
5	Do you agree that creative furniture are as durable as traditional furniture?	140(93.4)	10(6.7)	3.71	0.67	Agreed
6	Can creative furniture be personalized?	69(46.0)	81(54.0)	2.66	1.25	Agreed
7	Can creative furniture add to the general out look of the room space?	131(87.3)	19(12.7)	3.57	0.95	Agreed
8	Are creative furniture artistic, innovative and Modern?	144(96.0)	6(4.0)	3.70	0.65	Agreed
9	Can creative furniture add value to undervalued materials?	136(90.7)	14(9.3)	3.57	0.87	Agreed
10	Does creative furniture uplifts the mood in the living space?	139(92.7)	11(7.3)	3.59	0.80	Agreed

Field Survey, 2023

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research can be concluded that there was a high level of the acceptability of the use of utilization of wood cuttings for creative furnishing for economic developments irrespective of their income and it use in the home as a way of promoting our creativity.

In the quest for sustainable and innovative design solutions, the potential economic benefits of utilizing wood cuttings for creative furnishing designs for homes emerge as a captivating avenue. This comprehensive exploration has highlighted the intricate interplay between creativity, sustainability, and economics in the

realm of design. The repurposing of wood cuttings not only contributes to responsible resource management but also presents a viable business proposition with far-reaching implications.

The unique aesthetic opportunities offered by irregular wood cuttings showcase the potential for creativity and innovation in design, attracting a niche market while catering to broader consumer preferences for authenticity and individuality.

From an economic standpoint, the cost efficiency associated with using wood cuttings directly impacts profit margins and business sustainability. As consumers increasingly

prioritize eco-friendly products, repurposed wood furnishings emerge as a marketable commodity, commanding a premium due to their sustainability narrative. Moreover, the integration of repurposed wood cuttings offers the prospect of revitalizing local industries, fostering community development, and minimizing environmental footprints through localized material sourcing.

The use of creative furnishing from wood cuttings by the entrepreneurs will help to create more employment opportunity among the youth and elderly.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

Interior designers should collaborate with local woodworking industries and source high-quality wood cuttings. Consumers should be educated about the benefits of using wood cuttings in home furnishings. Highlight the environmental advantages, the unique aesthetic appeal, and the sustainable practices that go into creating each piece. Wood cutting furnishings can offer customization options for wood cutting furnishings. Because it will allow customers to choose from different wood types, finishes, and design elements to create personalized pieces that cater to their preferences and style. Designer should gather feedback from customers, designers, and stakeholders to continually improve their wood-cutting furnishings. Then they can use this feedback on designs, materials, and processes, ensuring that their creations meet and exceed expectations.

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